

BEYOND THE IMAGE: EXAMINING THE OVERLOOKED VARIABILITY IN FLOPPY DISK IMAGING PRACTICES

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Abstract – Disk imaging has become a common practice in the field of digital preservation. This process ensures a faithful capture and storage of digital content from a diverse range of storage media, including hard drives, flash storage and floppy disks. However, the field often takes for granted the perceived uniformity of disk images and their workflows. In our recent years working on ingest of portable storage media, we have been seeing a significant variability in how floppy disk images are created, processed and interpreted. This paper will explore this topic through case studies and highlight current technical and conceptual gaps that persist in the approach of the digital preservation field to disk images. Our findings emphasize the need for a more nuanced understanding of disk imaging, opening up a discussion to ensure more robust preservation outcomes.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Ingest workflows vary significantly between institutions. Differences in collecting policies and resourcing will lead digital preservation professionals to reasonably make different choices, even when working with the same types of carriers (in this context, carriers refer to digital removable media such as hard drives, floppy disks, flash storage, and other portable storage devices). This includes the method of copying the data itself; some

carriers can justifiably either be logically copied or disk imaged.

The older, rarer, and more vulnerable the carrier, the more likely, or indeed necessary, it is that disk imaging will be the chosen copy method. By creating a bit-by-bit copy of a carrier, disk imaging allows for the preservation and transfer of digital content from media that cannot be directly accessed using contemporary systems and can potentially capture additional content that a logical copy would miss, such as deleted files, or information on the file system.

Once that decision is made, it can often be seen as not needing further interrogation; ‘best practice’ is being followed by taking a disk image, and that process is unambiguous. While that may be relatively accurate for imaging more modern carriers, it is not the case when working with floppy disks. Despite the widespread adoption of disk imaging for these carriers, there is no commonly agreed ‘best practice’ that ensures optimal accuracy and reliability. Moreover, we argue that such a best practice cannot exist, and that it is neither necessary nor practical.

A key issue in the field is the assumption that disk images are inherently uniform and reliable. Default settings and widely used tools are often treated as producing ideal copies, yet our experience suggests that variability is the norm, particularly when working with media from outside the United States (U.S.). Different countries adopted computer

systems at different times, with varying hardware and software standards. For example, while IBM-compatible PCs and MS-DOS became dominant in the U.S. during the 1980s [1], other regions developed distinct computing ecosystems. In Japan and parts of Europe, the MSX-DOS standard played a major role [2], while the United Kingdom (U.K.) saw a thriving home computing scene built around systems like those running CP/M, a widely used operating system before the rise of MS-DOS [3]. These regional differences together with many commonly used tools being developed for a limited technical or geographic scope mean that it is difficult to develop a universally applicable workflow.

While experienced practitioners recognize these complexities, discussions about them remain limited, restricting knowledge-sharing within a select group of experts. Greater accessibility to these insights is essential to ensure a more collaborative and effective approach to disk imaging.

Different institutions and storage carriers require different disk imaging approaches tailored to their specific needs. While commonly used tools such as KryoFlux and FTK Imager exist, there is little discourse on the nuances of these tools and choice of settings. Each imaging scenario presents unique challenges, necessitating case-by-case decision-making rather than reliance on one-size-fits-all guidelines.

This paper addresses these concerns by exploring the variability and challenges of disk imaging of floppy disks through a series of case studies. By examining different approaches and their outcomes, we highlight the technical and conceptual gaps that persist in current practices. Our analysis aims to foster a more nuanced understanding of disk imaging, encouraging an inclusive and collaborative approach that ultimately leads to more robust preservation outcomes.

II. DIFFERENT DISK IMAGES

Before presenting our case studies, we thought it would be useful to summarize the different types of disk images [4].

Flux Stream Images: These capture the magnetic flux transitions of a disk, providing a raw representation of the data. They allow for highly accurate recreation of disk formats and

can be useful in recovering non-standard or obscure disk structures. These typically have file sizes an order of magnitude larger than the original content and require further processing before they can be used by most emulators. The other types below can be derived from flux stream images.

Bitstream images: An intermediate type which stores the low-level encoded bit stream of each track. These have a significantly lower file size than flux stream images but still need further processing before they can be used by most emulators. Sector-level images can be derived from bitstream images.

Sector-Level Images: These store data at the logical sector level, commonly used for standard disk replication. They do not capture low-level magnetic data but provide a functional representation of the disk's file system. This format is frequently used for creating accessible and easily emulated disk copies, and there is often human-readable data when viewed in a text editor.

Each type of disk image has distinct implications for long-term preservation, compatibility, and usability. No single format is inherently superior; while a flux stream image may capture the most data, this must be justified against the notable file size increase. Furthermore, the lack of discourse on the implications of choosing a particular format raises concerns. Preservation efforts must consider the specific needs of their institutions and communities when selecting disk imaging methods.

For the purposes of this paper, we are not treating 'forensic disk images' as their own type of disk image, considering these as containers or structures which hold one of the types described above, alongside additional information such as building in checksums to image files [5].

III. CASE STUDIES

The following case studies, presented in chronological order, illustrate our experiences with floppy disk imaging and the challenges encountered.

A. FC5025 controller and WANG/ICL 5.25-inch Disks (August 2023)

Our initial attempt at disk imaging utilized the FC5025 floppy controller [6], installed in the forensic

workstation, a FRED [7], at the Digital Preservation Lab at Cambridge University Library (CUL). Initial test results appeared promising, but when attempting to process a wider variety of disks from the collections at Churchill Archives Centre (CAC), the majority processed with errors even when we ran them against all supported disk types, and some disks could not be read at all. On review, while there was some human-readable data contained within the disks that read with errors, it was also apparent that a significant amount of data was missing from these copies.

The FC5025 relies on interpreting sector-level data for a set list of formats (see Table 1) and does not capture raw flux transitions, leading to imperfect copies when dealing with formats outside of this list. The FC5025 was also designed to work primarily with emulators, which are detailed on their website, and is very much focused on the U.S. market, where the controller was developed. Given the U.K.'s rich computing history, we encountered formats that the FC5025 was not designed for, limiting its effectiveness. Additionally, we discovered that cleaning floppy disk drives – especially for 5.25-inch disks – is fundamental, as dust and debris can build up easily, significantly impacting imaging accuracy, and this was complicated by the FC5025 and attached drive being integrated within the FRED workstation.

Table 1 – Formats accepted by FC5025

FC5025 Sector Formats
Apple DOS 3.2 (13-sector)
Apple ProDOS
Atari 810
Calcomp Vistagraphics 4500
Commodore 1541
Kaypro 2 CP/M 2.2
Kaypro 4 CP/M 2.2
MS-DOS
Motorola VersaDOS
North Star MDS-A-D
PMC MicroMate
Tandy Color Computer Disk BASIC
TI-99/4A

We quickly determined that the FC5025 would not be sufficient for our needs, but were it not for the nature of our collections, with the vast majority from the U.K. ecosystem, we could have easily concluded that the disks we could not read properly were damaged outliers, rather than being inherently incompatible with the controller we were using.

B. Amstrad 3-inch Disks (July 2024, March 2025)

Our work with 3.5- and 5.25-inch disks had generally resulted in images from which we could extract individual files without relying on an emulator to interpret the images. However, our understanding at the time was that this was not the case with the small number of Amstrad 3-inch disks in our collections, where we believed we required an emulator to access and appraise individual files. The emulator we were testing, Caprice [8], listed various disk formats it could mount, but the only one compatible with our controller's output was a sector-level '.dsk (disk image)'.

We captured flux images of the disks and attempted to convert these into usable sector-level images. Our first attempt, using the GreaseWeazle controller [9] (which we acquired after releasing the FC5025 was not sufficient for our needs) to generate a .dsk file from the flux images, did not work in the emulator, raising concerns about whether the disks we were working with were functional.

We were fortunate to find a blog detailing similar experiences from a retro computing enthusiast using the same controller for Amstrad disks [10]. They had chosen to perform the conversion from flux image to sector image using the HxC floppy emulator [11]. This is a tool we had used previously to assess the accuracy of floppy disk images, and it also allows for the conversion and export of different disk image types, including the 'CPC DSK file.' The resulting .dsk files generated with HxC loaded successfully into our emulator, revealing an important point: the .dsk extension is used differently by different applications.

It turns out that the 'CPC DSK file' format in HxC is an 'Extended CPC DSK' [12], which contains the same data as the .dsk file created by the GreaseWeazle controller but with additional structural elements. The GreaseWeazle can also create these files, but it does so with the '.edsk' extension. While this distinction may seem useful in a vacuum, it caused issues with Caprice, as the emulator has a strict list of formats that it will accept, necessitating manually editing the file extension in order to be able to use those files. Different approaches and uses of the 'standard' and

extended .dsk format can be seen from other tool developers [13], beyond those we use, underlining the lack of standard usage and terminology, despite the well-defined underlying specification.

Other emulators we tested later were able to handle both the non-extended version (i.e., a standard sector image) and the extended one. However, this only further highlights the risk that a copy, which initially seems sufficient – especially when tested with only a single use case – may be inadequate if an institution's needs later change.

C. Apple MFS Disks (December 2024)

By December 2024, after working with a sizable number of 3.5-, 5.25-, and 3-inch disks, the approach to disk imaging had begun to diverge between our two institutions. CUL opted to focus on the SCP (flux) approach for their work, aiming to capture the most detailed low-level data from the disks, which would allow for the highest degree of fidelity in the preservation process. Meanwhile, CAC, with an aim of avoiding unnecessarily large files for permanent preservation, and in line with similar approaches such as being satisfied with taking logical copies rather than disk images of simple, undamaged contemporary material, initially settled on imaging floppy disks as HFE bitstream images.

For the majority of floppy disks, this HFE approach proved to be effective and manageable. Our understanding was that this method required specifying the bitrate for each disk being imaged, but that was relatively straightforward to determine from the physical characteristics of the disks, and so not an important limitation. We still believe this to be the case for most floppy disks. However, as we found with more complex disk types, the method cannot be universally applied.

A case in point was CAC's attempt to create an HFE copy from an MFS-formatted Mac 400k disk. Assuming a bitrate of 250 kbit/s for a double-density disk, the resulting copy showed significantly fewer tracks than expected when analyzed in HxC (see Figure 1). This issue arose from the varying bitrate (or RPM) across tracks, which (at least at the time of writing) prevents the creation of a proper HFE copy directly with the GreaseWeazle controller [14]. To capture a full low-level copy in such cases, a flux copy

is necessary. This experience reinforced the understanding that disk imaging is not a static process but one that requires continuous testing, adaptation, and careful consideration of both preservation goals and technical limitations.

Notably, while the authors have worked together on developing their understanding of floppy disks and associated workflows, and the archive parts of our institutions are reasonably analogous, we have come to different conclusions. At CAC, the focus remains on utilizing HFE for all disks where that is appropriate, because of the balance it offers in terms of file size and data fidelity. For CUL, the move toward SCP was seen as essential for the most thorough preservation, ensuring the capture of all low-level disk data, even if it means dealing with larger file sizes.

Figure 1 - A Mac 400k MFS disk captured as a HFE bitstream image at 250 kbit/s, as displayed in HxC Floppy Emulator

IV. CONCLUSION

The process of disk imaging – particularly when dealing with legacy media like floppy disks – is far more nuanced and complex than most existing guidance suggests. A core issue we've identified is the scarcity of resources written specifically *by and for* archival and digital preservation professionals. Much of the available documentation is produced by adjacent communities – such as retro computing enthusiasts, gaming communities, or digital

forensics experts in law enforcement – whose goals, while overlapping at times, often diverge in subtle but important ways from those of cultural heritage preservation.

What's lacking is not only centralized, authoritative guidance that can lay a solid foundation, but also a broader public record of the divergent decisions for choices within workflows reached by different institutions working within distinct contexts. As our case studies have shown, there are choices to be made within disk formats, tools, and imaging techniques over which institutions can reasonably differ, creating a dynamic landscape that resists a one-size-fits-all or simple 'best practice' approach. Addressing this complexity requires both a grounded baseline and a visible spectrum of practices that reflect differing institutional priorities, regional computing histories, and collection-specific needs.

V. CALL FOR ACTION

The challenges we've encountered underscore the need for a more nuanced and collaborative approach to disk imaging within the archival community; one that is not rigidly bound to a one-size-fits-all methodology but instead embraces the diversity of storage media, formats, and regional computing histories.

As practitioners, we must acknowledge that no single approach to disk imaging will be universally applicable. Instead, we must foster an environment where knowledge-sharing and flexibility are paramount. This involves not only sharing specific methodologies and workflows but also contributing to the larger conversation about how we adapt our practices to the needs of particular collections, institutions, and regions. The diversity of disk formats, file systems, and computing ecosystems worldwide – such as the differences between U.S.-dominated systems and those developed in regions like the U.K., Japan, or Europe – demands that we move beyond standardized practices and consider the specific technical and contextual challenges of each situation.

There were moments, such as our early work with the FC5025, when we weren't sure whether the issues we faced stemmed from our inexperience or if there was something more systemic at play. Had

there been more openness in the community about workflows and challenges, it would have alleviated some of these uncertainties. The sharing of processes and insights from others could have reassured us that we weren't alone in facing such challenges. By exchanging experiences, we not only reduce the doubts that come with unfamiliar technologies but also help avoid reinventing the wheel or falling into common pitfalls that others have already navigated.

We encourage members of the digital preservation community to share their successes, challenges, and insights into disk imaging, whether in publications, conferences, or on their own websites. In particular, we see significant value in each organization which is able to publish their own workflows, so that those newly developing their capacity can look to peer institutions and understand what decisions have been made in an analogous environment. By doing so, we can work together to build a more comprehensive and inclusive knowledge base that benefits the entire community.

While centralized guidelines remain a helpful starting point, the diversity of media, formats, and use cases means that flexibility and continual testing are crucial, documenting the different contexts in which these practices are being applied. Every institution and collection is situated within its own unique history, geography, and technological landscape. By making explicit the specific circumstances – such as regional market influences, institutional priorities, and collection characteristics – we can ensure that the field's practices remain dynamic and reflective of the diverse challenges faced in digital preservation.

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